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Jowhar Massoudie and Gulriz Shinwari

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Green HRM as Predictor of Firm's Environmental Performance and Role of Employees' Environmental Organizational Citizenship Behavior as Moderator

Jowhar Massoudie
Gulriz Shinwari

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Abstract

*This study examines the effects of GHRM on environmental performance and the moderating role of environmental and organizational citizenship behavior in the telecommunications sector in Kabul, Afghanistan. The random sampling technique is used to collect the data from the corresponding respondents. Multiple regressions are used to obtain the study's numerical result. The result of the study is the following: The estimated coefficient of green recruitment and selection is 0.074, which is significantly high at 5 percent. These positive values indicate a positive relationship between environmental performance and green recruitment and selection. There is a significant relationship between environmental performance and green recruitment and selection. The top management commitment was found to have a significant ($p = 0.048$) estimate coefficient, where $p < 0.05$, so we rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis, green recruitment and selection and environmental performance have a significant relationship. There is a significant relationship between green performance management and environmental performance. A significant ($p = 0.002$) coefficient was found in green performance management, where $p < 0.05$. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis by stating that green management performance and environmental performance are essential. There is a significant relationship between training, development, and environmental performance. This study also employs a robust and indirect effect to investigate a valid mediation. The product of OBCE and Green Recruitment and Selection show a significant positive indirect effect of green environmental and organizational citizenship behavior in the relationship between environmental performance and green recruitment and selection, which accepts H4 of the study. The estimated coefficient of OBCE * Green Recruitment and Selection is 0.098. This implies that environmental and organizational citizenship behavior has played a critical role in the relationship between environmental performance and green recruitment and selection because the coefficient of OBCE * Green Recruitment and Selection is greater than the estimated coefficient of green selection and recruitment.*

Keywords: GHRM; OBCE; Environmental Performance; Telecommunication; Afghanistan

Introduction

Over the past few years, environmental problems such as environmental degradation, declining biodiversity, water pollution, global warming, and smog have become more critical. This raises serious concerns for sustainable environmental development. Companies contributing to environmental issues have developed relevant green initiatives for sustainable development. However, the practical implementation and support of green initiatives largely depend on the attitude of employees toward Environmental Organization Citizenship Behavior (OCBE) (Priyanka et al., 2018). Therefore, HRM specialists create a green workforce. There are challenges to doing, developing, and maintaining research (Ahmad et al., 2021).

The OCBE is defined as "personal behavior and decision-making that contribute to the effectiveness of environmental practices and are not explicitly recognized by formal work requirements" (Ahmad, 2021), including citizens' ecological participation. It contributes to employee eco-innovation and environmental attitudes (Boerl & Consequences, 2021). OCBE is a valuable addition to the company's green development strategy. Several studies have examined OCBE factors at the individual level, such as individual factors of company sustainability (Ecer et al., 2021). Only green human resource management, such as green education (Pham et al., 2018), green activity management (Pham et al., 2019), and employee engagement. In addition, the literature suggests that GHRM guidelines describe employee-friendly behavior through various social and psychological processes (Dumont et al., 2021). Modern industrialization's evolution, development, and operational environment have left an indelible mark on the environment: it has been recognized as a global issue. Many researchers noted that the awareness environment is deteriorating. Therefore, companies are pressured to comply with international agreements and treaties. The specificity of international environmental agreements and regulations is becoming increasingly important and complex. This significantly impacts the current business environment in terms of business growth. It is essential to pay attention to environmental concerns. It avoids behaviors that harm society, the economy, and the environment. This means we must focus on business development while also paying attention to the environment. The concept of environmental protection and management has re-emerged to reduce such pressures. Due to the increasing use of green products and the benefits of green management, many companies focus on green product development (GPD) and production. Therefore, it has a significant impact on a company's sustainability goals.

According to Ericot (2015), the innovation theory process aims to create market segments and profits through continuous technological and market knowledge. Behavior and decision-making processes arise from perceptual patterns. This is the starting point for creating new knowledge. Thus, when a company can identify patterns through experience and knowledge, it will combine to create a green corporate identity and vision. Moreover, entrepreneurship with market knowledge benefits entrepreneurs and generates marketing benefits (Ardiz et al., 2022). Ercot and Kaya (2016) argue that creating corporate social responsibility activities aimed at spreading awareness depends on the company's founding, the type of corporate culture, and the nature of the company's operations. Such initiatives require the knowledge of current and future employees to create and maintain a competitive advantage. Therefore, the company must integrate its management and employees to use innovative knowledge to gain a competitive advantage. From the above observations, this study describes the corporate social vision (GSV), the identity of green corporations, and employee-led green corporate citizenship behavior. However, formal rewards or a performance appraisal system cannot improve this behavior. Therefore, employee behavior in a company is often considered a critical factor in the success of green organization development.

Researchers and environmental policymakers worldwide agree that the causes of environmental degradation, such as lack of resources, increased pollution, and loss of biodiversity, are deeply rooted in human behavior (Mtutu & Thondhlana, 2021). Many organizations do little harm to their day-to-day operating environment by implementing environmental management systems (EMS) or green initiatives. Therefore, there is an emerging need to understand and shape employee behavior to minimize the negative environmental impact of organizational activities. The role of green human resource

management (HRM) in influencing green employee behavior in the workplace to address these concerns has become the subject of study (Dumont et al., 2016). Green HRM is about strengthening environmental awareness. It involves the HRM process of hiring, training, rewarding, and creating a green workforce that understands and values green values, practices, and initiatives. Humans in environmental performance have emphasized green employee behavior as a critical factor in successfully implementing environmental policy in the workplace (Kim et al., 2022). Employee environmental behavior, also known as corporate citizen behavior (OCBE), is the voluntary action of an individual that leads to effective environmental performance in an organization (Boerl & Pellil, 2012). Employees are needed for every organization. Studies on green HRM are currently more focused on the corporate sector than academia (Tyro, 2018). Green HRM is studied in the context of multinational corporations. It also pays little attention to environmental management in Asian countries. However, studies should be conducted to fill the literature gaps arising from economic and environmental sustainability issues in developing countries (Billig et al., 2020). Saadatian et al. (2009) claim that Malaysian research universities are already responsible for environmental sustainability. Furthermore, it is busy starting green exercises on university campuses. While several comprehensive studies have shed light on the current state of sustainability efforts in higher education institutions in the country, Muhammad et al. (2020) suggest that employee behavior in the higher education sector is vital in reducing environmental degradation and ensuring successful environmental performance with social impact.

Telecommunication sector emissions, however, are relatively low compared to the corporate sector. Nevertheless, educating current and future generations about the importance of environmental awareness, research, and behaviors that support the environment (Rainer & Morgan, 2021). More and more universities have incorporated environmental management issues into their policies when they know their environmental responsibilities—study and research projects. According to Ecer et al. (2021), the global proportion of university leaders and faculty must be aware of sustainable development and university practice. Moreover, integrating sustainability principles into curricula, research, and outreach programs requires little effort. Lausanne (2006) also highlights vital partners at the university. This includes the academic director, professors, and students. The concept of sustainable development should be included in the policies, procedures, and education of all members of these partners. In practice, it is almost impossible to integrate environmental sustainability into the initial system. Also, multiplication effects can benefit the early adoption of sustainability procedures. This can be achieved by identifying and supporting specific people involved in small projects to share their experiences and knowledge.

This study focused on the ability-motivation-opportunity theory (Bailey, Berg, & Calberg, 2000). This study aimed to explain the relationship between GHRM and OCBE practices. The GHRM guidelines for green training and environmental and friendly activity management will be explored using the mixed approach implemented in the telecommunications sector in Kabul, Afghanistan. Environmental impacts have been a significant concern for organizations and governments over the past few decades (Reid, Elliott, & Appham, 2021). In addition, current regulations and laws have increased the organization's awareness and experience in managing environmental issues. Therefore, environmental concerns have recently become a new topic in management scholarship (Masri & Jarron, 2022), emphasizing the integration of human resource management and environmental management strategies. Employee involvement in environmentally

responsible behavior is essential. In particular, the corporate citizenship approach to the environment helps solve environmental problems and supports the organization's sustainable development (Groot & Stig, 2022). Environmental sustainability management strategies are critical to improving environmental performance and maintaining competitive advantage (China and Hoso, 2021). In addition, implementing environmental practices can benefit hotel human resources, such as employee knowledge and environmental awareness. Encourage employees to be environmentally conscious and eager to adapt to the environment. (Chan, Hoon, Chan, and Okumo, 2021).

So far, scholars have published articles on GHRM and OCBE in various fields, including theoretical studies aimed at better understanding the current literature on GHRM (Ren, Tang, and Jackson, 2022), which examines the effects of GHRM on environmental performance (Gersey, Langoni, and Luzini). According to the theory of social exchange, if employees understand the support and benefits of a friendly practice environment. They voluntarily participate in green activities (Alt & Spitzbeck, 2016). Being green can encourage employees to make decisions about the environment. Several scientists, such as Penzon, Gersey, Lethbury, and Redman (2016), who studied the effects of GHRM practices on OCBE in the context of the UK healthcare system, have taken a similar view. Kim, Park, and Warner (2015) discuss the multiplication model application and highlight human resource engagement—management methods to execute the organization's activities. Remsdijk and Lewis (2013) also point to the influence of regulation that arises from a combination of competence and motivation. Apart from the capabilities and opportunities, it contributes to high-efficiency differences. Although there are previous studies on the importance of environmental management, there are some studies on the importance of environmental management.

Objectives of the Study

- To investigate the effects of the GHRM dimension on environmental performance.
- To scrutinize the moderating effects of environmental and organizational citizenship behavior on the relationship between the GHRM dimension and environmental performance.

2. Review of Literature

Green HRM and Environmental Performance

Previous studies have acknowledged the impact of green HRM on corporate environmental performance. For example, a study by Jabbar and Jabbar (2016) found that HRM green practices encourage companies to do better under environmental conditions. Research also shows that with green HRM, organizations can implement environmental management programs. Successfully implemented (e.g., Bangwal, Tiwari, and Chamula (2017), Rawasda (2018), and Gulal, Ashraf, Gilal, Gilal, and Chana (2019). Some studies have used green HRM as an intermediary between organizational factors and corporate environmental performance. For example, a study by Guerzi et al. (2016) found that green HRM plays a role in mediating stakeholder stress and ensuring solid environmental performance. Similarly, a study by Obidat et al. (2018) found that green HRM plays a role in mediating between higher management support and international relations. Overall, past research has shown that green HRM does not directly or indirectly play a key role in influencing an organization's environmental performance in Qatar's oil and gas industry.

Specific assumptions are as follows: H1: Green recruitment and selection significantly impact the company's environmental performance H2: Green training and development significantly impact the company's environmental performance. Green human resource management and the potential of this environment can be better understood in the context of opportunity promotion theory. This is one of the most popular theories in empirical studies to understand the effect of HRM exercise on organizational performance (Applebam, 2000; Boselli et al., 2021). AMO's theory explains that high performance (HPWS) is grouped into three essential aspects of different but relevant HR practices: competence, motivation, and opportunity (Applebam, 2022). This can be based on different actions, such as recruitment and selection. Furthermore, training and development programs provide employees with the knowledge and skills to perform specific tasks. Financial and non-financial incentives are aimed at maximizing employee efforts to achieve performance goals. Ultimately, an opportunity is a set of actions that increase engagement. Knowledge sharing and independence encourage employee participation in activities (Marin-Garcia & Thomas, 2022)

Chima and Javed (2021) examined the impact of corporate social responsibility, green HRM, and a sustainable environment in the textile industry. Pinzone et al. (2022) examined green HRM performance. The health sector has a shared emotional commitment to changing environmental management. And the attitude of total corporate citizenship towards the environment. Pham et al. (2019) explored the relationship between green learning. Green employee engagement Environmentally friendly performance management and hospitality at OCBE Uzdfc et al. (2020) conducted a GHRM study in the automotive industry. Environmentally friendly delivery chain management Environmental cooperation with buyers and suppliers Ragas et al. (2017) explored the relationship between implementing the GHRM approach and greener life. And performance in various private sectors. In return, Sang et al. (2020) examined how green HRM interacts with the relationship between green change leaders. Green innovation and environmental performance in SMEs in the manufacturing sector? Although AMO theory is the most comprehensive theory for understanding the role of green HRM in environmental performance, it is the most comprehensive theory for understanding the role of green HRM in environmental performance. However, preliminary studies have chosen the complete AMO framework in the research models. The communication mechanism between green HRM practices and environmental performance through corporate citizenship behavior should be more noticed. Harvey et al. (2022) and Ren et al. (2021) emphasize the need to explore the mediation process by which green HRM can generate long-term support. Thus, this study identified two literary gaps. 1) extending green HRM research to university contexts, and 2) examining the role of OCBE academic staff mediation between green HRM practices and university environmental performance based on the AMO framework.

Green competency exercises refer to green recruitment and selection and green training and development programs to improve employee environmental awareness and skills. To enable employees to identify environmental issues and take necessary steps to reduce adverse conditions (Taxira et al., 2021). According to Tang et al. (2017), green employment and selection have three aspects: employee awareness of green employer markings and green criteria for applicant selection. Employee environmental awareness is a crucial aspect of the green recruitment process. Because if the values of the employee environment align with the organization's values, employees are more likely to respond positively to corporate environmental concerns. Renwick et al. (2013) argue that job seekers prefer to work in reputable organizations with a good environment. Similarly, employers want to recruit candidates familiar with the environment because they are eager to participate in eco-initiatives (Jabbur et al., 2021). Taxira et al., 2022 also, environmental education and development programs are essential for improving

employee skills and attitudes toward environmental management. The importance of environmental protection increases our ability to adapt to change. Green education provides knowledge management that contributes to environmental knowledge and behavior while providing the ability to solve environmental problems. Exercises encouraging green incentives, including performance appraisals and awards, aim to motivate employees to align their environment with the organization's environmental goals (Harvey et al., 2021). Incorporating environmental responsibility into a performance management system provides employees with clear information about their expectations. Perform in Environmental Management Giving employees a systematic view of their environmental performance helps them develop their knowledge, skills, and abilities in environmental management (Jackson et al., 2011). The company will increase its commitment to environmental responsibility and encourage it to participate in corporate citizen behavior against the environment. (Govandarajolu and Daylo, 2021)

The Green Award for Encouraging Environmental Civil Behavior Among Employees may include financial and non-financial benefits such as recycling incentives. It provides flexible work schedules and communications to reduce travel costs. Provide free bicycles or pollution-free vehicles. Alternatively, linking growth opportunities to environmental performance (Jackson et al., 2022) and employee involvement in environmental activities (Rinwak et al., 2013). Using negative incentives can lead employees to take more responsibility for the organization's environmental problems (Tang et al., 2017). Green employee engagement exercises are designed to provide employee voice-raising opportunities in environmental management and offer solutions to environmental problems in organizations (Dobos & Dobos, 2021). Through open discussion, opportunities for participation contribute to the development of environmental culture in organizations. They exchange views and share perspectives on environmental issues (Alt & Spitzbeck, 2016). Tang et al. (2017) emphasized a clear vision of the formal environment and the dissemination of knowledge through formal and informal communication channels. This suggests that employees participate in environmental initiatives. The use of green teams is also an essential factor for organizations that aim to improve their environmental management practices. Share knowledge and offer new solutions to complex problems.

Green HRM and Green Recruitment and Selection

A study by Haridas and Sivasberman (2016) examined the degree of impact of green HRM practices on company performance. One of the independent variables tested is environmentally friendly recruitment. From the model used, the regression weakness for green deployment is 0.144, which means that a single increase in green deployment results in a 0.144 unit change (increase) in stable performance. If other independent variables are constant, the value of "t" is 2.119, significant at .05. This green highlight shows that hiring positively impacts a company's performance. The findings are consistent with the findings of Bhutto and Orenzeb (2016), who examined the effects of environmentally friendly human resource management on the performance of companies using Pakistani companies. Moreover, he found that hiring environmentally friendly staff positively impacted the company's performance. A study by Sriram and Saba (2020) found that eco-human resource management practices are essential for promoting organizational interests. The study adds that green human resources can save the environment from natural damage, but research has shown that some employees find it challenging to manage environmentally friendly human resources. Another study by Javed and Cheema (2017) examined the impact of choosing environmentally friendly HRM in the agricultural industry. Among other environmentally friendly HRM practices, studies have examined environmentally friendly selection and its effects on agriculture. Environmentally friendly placement and selection are positively linked to organizational

outcomes. Because the agricultural sector directly depends on the environment, Eco-friendly hiring and selection practices in this industry have mutual benefits. First, they can help protect the environment. Furthermore, second, to help agricultural companies achieve better performance.

This study examined the effect of green HRM in working OCB environments. The reason for environmental OCBs is that traditional job descriptions often need to cover only some aspects of the job, especially in the environmental field. Therefore, implementing the concept of OCB is vital because it relies on the voluntary participation of employees in such behavior. Few studies have reported a positive effect of green HRM on the employee OCB environment and related perceptions. For example, a study by Harvey et al. (2013) reported a positive correlation between HRM practices, environmental performance, and organizational citizenship behavior. These concepts may have some theoretical variations. However, the general view is that employees are internally motivated to protect the natural environment and make the corporate environment program successful. The relationship between the green HRM and the employee OCB environment is also supported by the AMO model (Applebam, Bailey, Berg, & Kalberg, 2000). Therefore, employee performance is determined by ability, motivation, and opportunity. These three elements can be improved by using green HRM practices. Ultimately, because green HRM affects both the company's environmental performance and its employees' green behavior, it is thought that the OCB environment, which is the sensitive behavior of the employee environment, plays a mediating role in this relationship. Employee behavior is often specific to a company's performance, so the role of the OCB environment mediator in this relationship is meaningful.

Effect of Green HRM on Employee OCB-Environment

Previous studies have shown that green HRM not only affects an organization's overall environmental performance but also impacts the employee's green behavior. Moreover, many authors use different labels in this study, such as green role behavior or green behavior (Pell et al., 2014). We apply the concept of civic behavior to the employee organization and environment. It is defined as the social behavior and appreciation of the individual, which is not recognized by the formal reward system and contributes to the effective management of the environment by organizations (Boerl & Pyle, 2022)—categories such as information sharing to prevent workplace pollution. Increased participation in green practices, green concepts, and more, the theoretical basis of the OCB environment is based on the OCB literature, which explains the voluntary behavior of employees that is essential for the proper functioning of the organization (Nihaf, 2021).

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Green Training and Development and Environmental Performance

In order to enhance employee knowledge and skills by the requirements of the corporations. Organizational training and human resource development must be carried out systematically and continuously, and knowledge and skills related to environmental sustainability and green technologies must be emphasized as core content. Green training and development encourages the dissemination of environmental values among employees and enables employees to participate in voluntary behavior (Boerl, 2020). This will improve your ability to identify environmental issues (Gondarajolo and Day, 2021). This reduces the adverse effects on the environment. Employee involvement in environmental activities (Place, Mike, and Stall, 2021) provides employees with an understanding of field environmental standards. Moreover, be aware of ways to reduce the negative environmental impact. Through green training, they can test the knowledge and skills of employees.

How do you prepare and maintain a work environment? It has already been established that the general development of employee behavior, attitudes, skills, and knowledge affects the termination of environmental cooperation and its performance, subject to joint training and development. Previous studies have shown that green training and development helps provide a diverse workforce by developing the knowledge, skills, and competencies needed for innovation. This enhances the performance of the organization. Organizational competence is also greatly influenced by the level of staff training. Training builds knowledge and skills in employees. The organization needs to achieve its goals and objectives and increase productivity. A cross-sectional study of employee skills and competencies about employee performance explains that the performance of an organization is the result of the entire company's operations. The performance here can be assessed by analyzing the company's current behavior, particularly in terms of efficiency and effectiveness in general. As suggested by the organization RBV, improving competition and profitability depends on factors that affect the organization's strategic resources. In theory, RBV links green human resource management and environmental performance. Here, the main goal of GHRM is to provide education and development. It also provides incentives and new opportunities for the company to demonstrate better competitive behavior to maintain a competitive advantage and better performance than its competitors. These unacceptable organizations' resources come together to create high-level resources. This type of high-discipline method gives companies a competitive advantage. Moreover, that can be called competence. These capabilities are viewed from three different perspectives: physical capital, human capital, and social capital. Researchers emphasize that environmentally friendly education is very effective in achieving greater sustainability regarding EMS effectiveness. Quantitative studies have concluded that green education is one of the main strategies or mechanisms to prevent climate change. The first assumption is based on the above reasons, as it encourages the systematic development of low-carbon products by businesses.

Green Performance Management and Environmental Performance

Performance assessments that assess daily and structured tasks are no longer relevant in international relations. Human resource performance assessments are increasingly focused on the achievements of individuals or groups in innovation and technology. A green performance management strategy seeks to evaluate employee environmental performance. Engage them in corporate environmental activities (Rinwak et al., 2021).

Environmental perspectives from managers and executives help build the understanding, knowledge, skills, and competencies that motivate employees to take environmental responsibility. (Gwandarajolu and Dayalo, 2022). Therefore, monitoring and evaluating employee performance in environmental activities will help employees become aware of green volunteerism and responsibility. To the environment (Chinander, 2021). Another green exercise is the participation of green workers. Green incentives through employee engagement encourage employees to participate in ecological activities and start new thinking. Help them implement their organization's environmental priorities. They are creating an effective environmental management system for sustainable efficiency (Boerl and Results, 2021). Therefore, employees are more interested in bidding on environmental projects if allowed to make decisions and advise on environmental issues (Penzon, 2022). According to Trail et al. (2001), OCBE is critical for implementing an EMS and integrating environmental policy with workplace practices.

Boerl and Pyle (2022) defined behavior that supports the environment in three dimensions, for example, by contributing to the environment. First, the ECO initiative is an employee-level initiative that mitigates environmental impacts in the workplace, such as recycling paper—disposal of waste in appropriate packages. The second includes employee organizational initiatives such as eco-citizen participation and employee participation in green activities and projects created by the company. Promote eco-friendly corporate reputation and volunteer participant organization environment. Steel activities ultimately include encouraging partners to protect the environment through eco-assistance. Such attitudes relate to mutual employee support, such as voluntarily sharing ideas and specialization in corporate environmental issues. Researchers have studied the OCBE of employees in various industries. For example, Boerl and others (2021) examined the impact of OCBEs on managers in manufacturing companies. Moreover, found a significant correlation between managers' involvement in OCBE and the organization's environmental management practices. Similarly, results and more (2014) examined the appropriate environmental behavior of first-line employees in Chinese manufacturing organizations. It demonstrated experimentally that OCBE had a positive impact on the environmental performance of this organization. While the studies mentioned above examined the OCBE-environmental effectiveness relationship in the context of the producer organization, this link has not been tested for the University Faculty of Environmental Activities OCBE. According to Rainer and Morgan (2022), it is not known whether university employees are more or less engaged in environmental behavior than industrial workers.

Green Human Resource Management and OCBE

GHRM is an integral part of a green management system. It is a new management philosophy and style that uses a management approach that applies the concept of "green" to human resource management to achieve corporate environmental management's strategic goals (Tang et al. , 2017). GHRM is a set of activities encouraging and coordinating, such as green recruitment. Green training Eco-friendly performance evaluation and green awards aimed at creating green values. Green knowledge and green skills while encouraging employees to participate in corporate social responsibility practices and improving the environmental performance of organizations (Tang et al., 2021). Many scholars argue that GHRM is the key to successfully implementing green strategies and environmental management practices (Renwick et al., 2016). GHRM reflects HRM in environmental management, emphasizing the role of HRM in preventing and controlling pollution in corporate operations and environmental protection (Tang et al., 2015). Therefore, GHRM has become a new topic in corporate environmental

management. OCBEs are voluntary social behaviors not determined by formal compensation systems and regulations. Nevertheless, it also enhances the efficiency of the organization's environmental management (Pell et al., 2022). The corporate environment, external social environment, and leadership style significantly impact an individual's OCBE (Lane et al., 2015). However, research on how GHRM affects OCBE has not received much attention. This study suggests that GHRM affects OCBE for several reasons. Green training can be identified as an entrepreneurial resource that defines employee values on the green. Develop knowledge and skills and help them participate in green activities (Tang et al., 2021). Second, HRM theory proposes an understanding of the need for employees to be effective in HRM practices in workplace behavior guidelines) Has to choose such practices (Ch., 2019 N. Nishi et al., 2008. a) Implementing the GHRM Code of Conduct can demonstrate the organization's commitment to environmental protection and therefore encourages employees to adopt a green attitude. Third, promote GHRM practices such as environmental assessment, green rewards, and compensation. Encourage employees to participate in active environmental protection practices. Give a sense of appreciation and value. Therefore, employees are compelled and encouraged to engage in green behavior voluntarily (Saeed et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2021).

3. Research Methodology

Research design

The research design is an action plan based on research objectives and guides the selection of resources and data types. Akobeng (2017) defines the research design as setting the conditions for collecting and analyzing data in a way that is intended to combine the suitability of the research objective with the economic procedure. Alvi and Senbeta (2017) said that the research design does not involve a specific data collection method or any specific type of data. Any data use either quantitative or qualitative data for data analysis purposes. This study adopts a quantitative research method to obtain the study's empirical result. The key features of quantitative research include formal and systematic measurement and the use of statistical data. The study uses this design to analyze the impact and relationship between foreign financial aid and poverty in Afghanistan. For this research, a quantitative method was used. The quantitative approaches in this research are primarily answers to the first, second, and third hypotheses. It can be seen from the research objective that focuses on the effects of green human resources management on environmental performance with the moderating role of environmental and organizational citizenship behavior of employees in the telecommunication sector in Kabul, Afghanistan.

Research Approach

As we already mentioned that this study will examine the effects of green human resource management on environmental performance in the telecommunication sector in Kabul, Afghanistan. The study's main objectives are as follows: first, to examine the effects of green recruitment and selection practices on environmental performance. Secondly, to investigate the effects of green management performance on environmental performance. Thirdly, to examine the effects of green training and development practices on environmental performance. Finally, this study will test the effects of environmental and organizational citizenship behavior on the relationship between environmental performance and green performance management practices. Therefore, the approach that we will follow in this study is deductive, in which the researcher starts from more general to more specific.

Research Philosophy

This study adopts an interpretivism philosophy while studying the topic of descriptive study on the environmental performance of the telecommunication sector in Nangarhar, Afghanistan. This philosophy is adopted because it allows using quantitative research methods—the primary data collected through a questionnaire. The interpretivism philosophy is associated with high validity because data tends to be trustworthy and honest. An interpretivism research philosophy is followed in this study because phenomena such as environmental performance can be explained through this philosophy. The quantitative research method is used in this study, which is more appropriate with an interpretivism approach. The interpretivism perspective is highly suitable when looking at businesses from the perspective of different people. Also, this study aims to create a new and broader understanding of customary sustainability, that is, to allow for adopting the interpretivism research philosophy.

Population

The population is generally an extensive collection of people or objects that is the main focus of a scientific query. All individuals or objects within a specific population usually have a common bond and characteristic or trait, or a group of individuals of the same species living and interbreeding within a given area. If a company wanted to know whether each of its 50,000 customers served during the year was satisfied, it might be challenging, costly, and impractical to call each client on the phone to conduct a survey. Since the characteristics of every individual in a population cannot be measured due to constraints of time, resources, and accessibility, a sample of the population is taken. In this case, 50000 clients are the population for the mentioned company. Our population of the study is the telecommunication sector and the included companies. The population is the senior and intermediate-level employees working in the telecommunication sector in Kabul province, Afghanistan. We will do sampling from the above population and collect their related data. The population in the telecommunication sector is 950 employees at senior and intermediate level managers working in the telecommunication sector in Kabul, Afghanistan.

Samples and Sampling Techniques

This study used a simple random sampling technique. The proven sampling technique was used to categorize managers into upper, middle, and lower managers, and finally, a simple sampling technique was used to select managers from each class. Based on the above arguments, the following table represents the sample size. The population is 950, so the sample size must be 274 per the Krejcie & Morgan sample rule.

Table 1: Sample Size of the Study

Telecommunication Networks	Number of employees
AWCC Telecommunication Sector	77
Etisalat Telecommunication Sector	47
Roshan Telecommunication Sector	54
Salam Telecommunication Sector	50
MTN Telecommunication Sector	46
Total Number of Employees	274

Source: Data output from SPSS

Unit of Analysis

As the study examines the effects of GHRM on environmental performance in the telecommunications sector in Kabul, Afghanistan, for this purpose, data is collected from the

managers at different levels of the telecommunications sector in Kabul, Afghanistan. Based on this argument, the data would be collected from the individuals working in these organizations. The unit of analysis is the managers (senior and intermediate-level individuals) working in the telecommunications sector in Kabul, Afghanistan. The individual's perceptions, ideas, and experiences would help us analyze the data.

Model Specification

Various statistical tools and techniques will be used for data analysis. The following is the model to be estimated.

$$EP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GRS + \beta_2 GTD + \beta_3 GPM + \beta_4 OBEC + \beta_5 OBEC * GRS + \beta_6 OBEC * GTD + \beta_7 OBEC * GPM + \epsilon$$

Where,

EP= Environmental Performance

GRS= Green Recruitment and Selection

GTD = Green Training and Development

GPM= Green Performance Management

OBEC = Environmental Organizational Citizenship Behavior

ϵ = Error Term

4. Statistics and Data Description

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics summarize the collected information from the respondents of the study. This gives an idea about the collected information that either the information is suitable for the estimation and further procedure or not. The tables below show the descriptive statistics by representing the total observations, minimum value, minimum value, and mean and standard deviation for each table. It can be seen that all the variables have 274 observations. The green training and development mean value is 3.012, given the standard deviation of -0.258. The maximum value of the variable is 5, while its minimum value is 1. Similarly, the mean value of green recruitment and selection is 2.054, given the standard deviation of 0.147. The maximum value of the variable is 5, while the minimum value is 1. Identically, the mean value of green performance management is 2.987, given the standard deviation of 0.258. The maximum value of the variable is 5, while the minimum value is 1. Similarly, the mean value of environmental performance is 2.147, given the standard deviation of 0.369. The maximum value of the variable is 5, while the minimum value is 1.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Green Training and Development	274	1	5	3.01	-0.25
Green Recruitment and Selection	274	1	5	2.05	0.14
Green Performance Management	274	1	5	2.98	0.25
Environmental Performance	274	1	5	2.14	0.36
OBCE	274	1	5	3.12	0.96
Valid N (listwise)	274				

Source: Data output from SPSS

Correlation Matrix

Correlation shows the relationship between two variables. This shows the direction and as well as the magnitude of the correlation. The correlation coefficient between

environmental performance and green recruitment and selection is 63 percent. This implies that green recruitment and selection are positively correlated with environmental performance. If there is an increase in green recruitment and selection, this will cause the environmental performance of the telecommunications sector in Kabul, Afghanistan, to improve. The correlation coefficient between environmental performance and green performance management is 52 percent. This implies that green performance management is positively correlated with environmental performance. If there is an increase in green performance management, this will cause the environmental performance of the telecommunications sector in Kabul, Afghanistan, to improve. Similarly, the correlation coefficient between environmental performance and green training and development is 37 percent. This implies that green training and development are positively correlated with environmental performance. If there is an increase in green training and development, this will cause to rise in the environmental performance of the telecommunication sector in Kabul, Afghanistan.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix of the Study

Variables		1	2	3	4	5
Environmental Performance	Pearson Correlation	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
Green Selection and Recruitment	Pearson Correlation	0.63	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.04				
Green Performance Management	Pearson Correlation	0.52	0.25	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.04	0.05			
Green Training and Development	Pearson Correlation	0.37	0.45	0.67	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.04	0.00	0.12		
EOCB	Pearson Correlation	0.48	0.36	0.47	0.12	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.04	0.00	0.04	0.02	

Source: Data output from SPSS

Model Summary

In this study, a regression analysis was conducted to determine the scope of use of GHRM and its effects on the environmental performance of the telecommunication sector in Kabul, Afghanistan. R is the value of the correlation coefficient between models. In our case, R indicates the relation between the estimated and actual value of the dependent variable, which is environmental performance. R-Square represents a measure of deviation in the efficiency of an organization that shows how independent variables of the study in the dependent variable bring many variations. The adjusted R2 value is 0.732, indicating that dropping or adding some study variables might cause the R-square to be raised or declined. As we mentioned before, R-square explains the study's independent variable on the dependent variable. This shows that 73.6 percent variation in the study's dependent variable is due to the independent variable, and the remaining portion goes to the error term.

Table 4: Model Summary of the Study

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.69	0.73	0.73	0.03

Source: Data output from SPSS

Analysis of the Variance (ANOVA)

Variance analysis was performed to test whether the model was adequate to predict the outcome compared to devise use. The F-ratio indicates the ratio of improvement in the estimate, resulting in the model being accurate. The F-ratio is 214.656 and

significant ($p < .05$). This model significantly improved the ability to assess the effects of GHRM on the environmental performance of the telecommunication sector in Kabul, Afghanistan. In precise, F-statistics measure the overall validity of the model. The overall model is well fit because the probability is lower than the significance level.

Table 5: Analysis of the Variance

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	228.65	6	147.36	214.56	0.03
Residual	352.58	268	8.35		
Total	581.23	274			

Source: Data output from SPSS

Regression Result

The regression result shows the effects of independent variables on the study's dependent variable. The estimated green recruitment and selection coefficient is 0.074, significant at 5 percent. These positive values indicate a positive relationship between environmental performance and green recruitment and selection. There is a significant relationship between environmental performance and green recruitment and selection. The top management commitment was found to have a significant ($p = 0.048$) estimate coefficient, where $p < 0.05$, so we rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis, green recruitment and selection and environmental performance have a significant relationship. There is a significant relationship between green performance management and environmental performance. A significant ($p = 0.002$) coefficient was found in green performance management, where $p < 0.05$. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis by stating that green management performance and environmental performance are essential. There is a significant relationship between training, development, and environmental performance. The coefficient of the green training and development estimate ($p = 0.023$) is $p < 0.05$, so the research here turned out to be $p < 0.05$, so we rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis, stating that there was an essential relationship between green training and development and environmental performance.

This study also employed a robust and indirect effect to investigate a valid mediation. The product of OBCE and Green Recruitment and Selection show a significant positive indirect effect of green environment and organizational citizenship behaviors in the relationship between environmental performance and green recruitment and selection, which accepts H4 of the study. The estimated coefficient of OBCE * Green Recruitment and Selection is 0.098. This implies that environmental and organizational citizenship behavior has played a critical role in the relationship between environmental performance and green recruitment and selection because the coefficient of OBCE * Green Recruitment and Selection is greater than the estimated coefficient of green selection and recruitment. Thus, organizational environmental citizenship behavior is a moderating variable. Identically, this study also employs a robust and indirect effect to investigate a valid mediation. The OBCE * Green Performance Management shows a significant positive indirect effect of green environment and organizational citizenship behaviors in the relationship between environmental performance and green performance management, which accepts H5 of the study. The estimated coefficient of OBCE and green performance management is 0.121. This implies that environmental and organizational citizenship

behavior has played a critical role in the relationship between environmental performance and green performance management because the coefficient of OBCE * green performance management is greater than the estimated coefficient of green performance management.

Thus, organizational environmental citizenship behavior is a moderating variable. This study employs a robust and indirect effect to investigate a valid mediation. The OBCE * Green training and development show a significant positive indirect effect of green environment and organizational citizenship behaviors in the relationship between environmental performance and green training and development, which accepts H6 of the study. The estimated coefficient of OBCE * green training and development are 0.087, which implies that environmental and organizational citizenship behavior has played a critical role in the relationship between environmental performance and green training and development because the coefficient of OBCE * green training and development is greater than the estimated coefficient of green training and development. Thus, organizational environmental citizenship behavior is a moderating variable.

Conclusion

This study examines the effects of GHRM on environmental performance and the moderating role of environmental and organizational citizenship behavior in the telecommunications sector in Kabul, Afghanistan. The random sampling technique is used to collect the data from the corresponding respondents. Multiple regressions are used to obtain the study's numerical result. The result of the study is the following: The estimated coefficient of green recruitment and selection is 0.074, which is significantly high at 5 percent. This positive value indicates a positive relationship between environmental performance and green recruitment and selection. There is a significant relationship between environmental performance and green recruitment and selection. The top management commitment was found to have a significant ($p = 0.048$) estimate coefficient, where $p < 0.05$, so we rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis; green recruitment and selection and environmental performance have a significant relationship. There is a significant relationship between green performance management and environmental performance. A significant ($p = 0.002$) coefficient was found in green performance management, where $p < 0.05$. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis by stating that green management performance and environmental performance are essential. There is a significant relationship between training, development, and environmental performance. The coefficient of the green training and development estimate ($p = 0.023$) is $p < 0.05$, so the research here turned out to be $p < 0.05$, so we rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis, stating that there was an essential relationship between green training and development and environmental performance.

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the coefficient of OBCE * Green Recruitment and Selection is greater than the estimated coefficient of green selection and recruitment. Thus, organizational environmental citizenship behavior is a moderating variable. Identically, this study also employs a robust and indirect effect to investigate a valid mediation. The OBCE * Green Performance Management shows a significant positive indirect effect of green environmental and organizational citizenship behavior in the relationship between environmental performance and green performance management, which accepts H5 of the study. The estimated coefficient of OBCE and green performance management is 0.121. This implies that environmental and organizational citizenship behavior has played a critical role in the relationship between environmental performance and green performance management because the coefficient of OBCE green performance management is greater than the estimated coefficient of green performance management. Thus, organizational environmental citizenship behavior is a moderating variable. This study employs a robust and indirect effect to investigate a valid mediation. The OBCE * Green training and development show a significant positive indirect effect of green environmental and organizational citizenship behavior in the relationship between environmental performance and green training and development, which accepts H6 of the study. The estimated coefficient of OBCE-Green training and development is 0.087. This implies that environmental and organizational citizenship behavior has played a critical role in the relationship between environmental performance and green training and development because the coefficient of OBCE * green training and development is greater than the estimated coefficient of green training and development. Thus, organizational environmental citizenship behavior is a moderating variable.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, First, our study connects green HRM practices with environmental performance through the moderating role of the OCBE framework. Our results show that green HRM practices promote positive environmental performance. Therefore, this study contributes to the expansion of the concept of OCBE by suggesting that the telecommunications sector enhances environmental performance through environmentally green HRM practices. Second, as far as we know, an EOCE effort has been made to examine the effects of environmental insanity on the relationship between green HRM practices and environmental performance. In particular, our study suggests that a more significant interest in the environment among employees contributes significantly to environmental performance and sustainability. Third, understanding the effects of green HRM practices on environmental performance through employee environmental incentives when personal values are in line with the values that the organization presents. It positively affects the behavior and attitudes of employees" (Edwards & Ship, 2007, p. 128). There is enthusiasm for the environment among people working in the telecommunications sector in Kabul, Afghanistan.

Environmental problems. Because the environmental problems of key partners cannot be avoided, current research shows that higher education institutions need to incorporate environmentally friendly practices into their activities to address environmental issues. This will allow employees to take pride in thinking about their organization's role in protecting the environment. This will not only increase employee loyalty to the organization. It also boosts reputation and financial performance. Therefore, higher education institutions must follow human resource management practices by the environment to achieve green management goals. Finally, this research encourages

corporate executives to identify critical organizational values for environmental management when designing environmentally friendly human resource management procedures. New talent must be recruited with a commitment to protecting the environment and promoting green values. Therefore, it is recommended that higher education professionals design their recruitment policy accordingly to recruit active personnel and evaluate their behavior—appropriate environmental friendliness of employees to achieve sustainable environmental performance.

Implications

Insights from this research might guide HR in developing strategies to boost employee happiness at work and productivity. Employers and administrators may utilize some essential factors contributing to environmental performance. The organizations must encompass informed choices and policies that consider the organization's strengths and potential. The research results will help employers gauge how happy and productive their staff is and how best to put them to work.

Authors Contributions

The authors confirm their contribution to the paper as follows: study conception, data collection, model evaluation, analysis, and design: JM; interpretation of results and draft manuscript preparation: GS. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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About the Authors

Mr. Jowhar Massoudie, Academic Administrator Department of Economics, Kardan University, Kabul, Afghanistan. <j.massoudi@kardan.edu.af> ORCID: 0009-0006-6058-9939

Mr. Gulriz Shinwari, Alumni MBA, and Member Research Society, Kardan University, Kabul, Afghanistan, and Manager Pashtany Bank (Gulbahar Center Branch) Kabul Afghanistan. <gulrizshinwari7@gmail.com> ORCID: 0009-0003-7228-6191
